

A Study on the Coincidence Phenomenon Between the Incenter and the Orthocenter of a Triangle Generated from the Intersections of a Triangle and Circles

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1 Abstract

We study a configuration arising from the intersections of a triangle and circles with the side lines as diameters. For a triangle ABC , let D , E , and F be the second intersection points of the circles with diameters BC , CA , and AB , respectively. Let P , Q , and R be the incenters of $\triangle ADF$, $\triangle BDE$, and $\triangle CEF$. We prove that the orthocenter of $\triangle PQR$ coincides with the incenter of $\triangle ABC$. Several associated similarity relations and geometric identities are also obtained, including a ratio product identity and an inequality involving the segments determined by P , Q , and R .

Figure 1: descriptive captions 1

2 Introduction

The study of special points associated with a triangle has a long and rich history in classical geometry. Among these, the so-called *triangle centers* play a fundamental role. One of the earliest and most celebrated results in this direction is due to Leonhard Euler, who proved that the circumcenter, centroid, and orthocenter of a triangle lie on a single straight

line, now known as the *Euler line*. This discovery initiated systematic investigations of geometric relations among triangle centers.

During the nineteenth century, triangle geometry was further developed by mathematicians such as Jakob Steiner and others, who studied various configurations involving circles, concurrency, and similarity. These works revealed that many remarkable geometric structures arise from simple constructions associated with a triangle.

Another classical result that has inspired many later investigations is *Napoleon's theorem*. This theorem states that if equilateral triangles are constructed externally on the sides of an arbitrary triangle, then the centroids of those equilateral triangles form an equilateral triangle. Such results illustrate that new triangles derived from a given triangle may exhibit unexpected geometric properties.

In the twentieth century, triangle geometry was systematized and extended. For example, Coxeter and Greitzer [?] summarized numerous classical results in their well-known book *Geometry Revisited*. More recently, Kimberling introduced the *Encyclopedia of Triangle Centers*, which catalogs thousands of triangle centers defined by various geometric constructions. These developments highlight the richness of the relationships among triangle centers.

A natural problem in this area is to investigate configurations in which triangle centers exhibit special coincidences or unexpected relationships. In general, the classical centers of a triangle (such as the centroid, circumcenter, orthocenter, and incenter) do not coincide except in highly symmetric cases such as the equilateral triangle. Therefore, it is of interest to construct new geometric configurations in which a center of a derived triangle coincides with a center of the original triangle.

In this paper, we study a configuration determined by three circles whose diameters are the sides of a given triangle. From the intersection points of these circles we construct three auxiliary triangles and consider their incenters. Our main result shows that the orthocenter of the triangle formed by these incenters coincides with the incenter of the original triangle. This phenomenon provides a new example of a geometric configuration in which centers of different triangles coincide in a nontrivial manner.

3 Proof

Main Theorem

Let $\triangle ABC$ be an arbitrary triangle. Let C_1, C_2, C_3 be the circles with diameters AB, BC, CA , respectively.

Let D be the intersection point of C_2 and C_3 different from C , E the intersection point of C_3 and C_1 different from A , and F the intersection point of C_1 and C_2 different from B .

Let P, Q, R be the incenters of $\triangle ADF$, $\triangle BDE$, and $\triangle CEF$, respectively. Let H be the orthocenter of $\triangle PQR$. Then H coincides with the incenter I of $\triangle ABC$.

(i) Case of an Acute $\triangle ABC$

Proof. We shall show that the point P lies on the straight line AI .

From the properties of the incenter in $\triangle ABC$, we have:

$$\angle BAI = \angle CAI = \frac{1}{2}\angle BAC, \quad \angle ABI = \angle CBI = \frac{1}{2}\angle ABC. \quad (2.1)$$

In $\triangle ADF$, from the same property of the incenter,

$$\angle DAP = \angle FAP = \frac{1}{2}\angle DAF, \quad \angle ADP = \angle FDP = \frac{1}{2}\angle ADF. \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2: descriptive captions 2

lemma 1. When $\triangle ABC$ is acute, let D be the intersection point of C_2 (the circle with diameter BC) and C_3 (the circle with diameter CA) that is not a vertex of $\triangle ABC$. Then D lies on the side AB and is the foot of the perpendicular from C to AB . Similarly, the intersection E of C_3 and C_1 (not a vertex) lies on BC , and the intersection F of C_1 and C_2 lies on CA .

Proof of Lemma 1. Since $\triangle ABC$ is acute, each vertex lies either inside or outside of the circle having the opposite side as diameter. A line through a vertex and the endpoint

of such a diameter intersects the circle at two points (see figure). In particular, C_2 and C_3 are two circles sharing the point C , and have another intersection point D (distinct from C since the triangle is acute). Because D lies on C_2 , the theorem of the inscribed angle implies that

$$\angle BDC = 90^\circ.$$

Similarly, since D lies on C_3 , we have

$$\angle ADC = 90^\circ.$$

Thus AD and BD are both perpendicular to DC . Since two lines perpendicular to the same line must coincide, we have A, D, B collinear; that is, $D \in AB$. Furthermore, since $AD \perp DC$, the point D is the foot of the perpendicular from C to AB .

By applying the same reasoning (using the inscribed angle theorem) to the other pairs of circles, we find that E and F are the feet of the perpendiculars from the respective vertices onto the opposite sides. Therefore, the lemma is proved. \square

From Lemma 1, equations (2.1) and (2.2) hold on the same straight line, and hence the point P lies on line AI . Similarly, Q lies on BI and R lies on CI . Let us denote the angles of $\triangle ABC$ by

$$\angle BAC = 2\alpha, \quad \angle ABC = 2\beta, \quad \angle ACB = 2\gamma.$$

Step 1. Show that

$$\angle PRQ = 90^\circ - \gamma, \quad \angle PQR = 90^\circ - \beta, \quad \angle QPR = 90^\circ - \alpha.$$

First, consider $\angle PRQ = 90^\circ - \gamma$.

From Lemma 1, the intersection point of the lines AE , BF , and CD is the orthocenter of $\triangle ABC$.

Since the four points B, C, F, D are concyclic, the three points A, B, C are excenters of $\triangle DEF$.

Figure 3: descriptive captions 3

The triangles $\triangle ABE$ and $\triangle CBD$ share the common angle $\angle ABC$, and since $\angle AED = \angle CDB - 90^\circ$, they are similar. Hence, $\triangle EBD \sim \triangle ABC$. Likewise, $\triangle EFC \sim \triangle ABC$ and $\triangle AFD \sim \triangle ABC$.

Therefore,

$$\angle DEF = 180^\circ - (\angle BED + \angle CEF).$$

Recalling that $\triangle EBD \sim \triangle EFC$, we obtain

$$\angle DEF = 180^\circ - (\angle BED + \angle CEF) = 180^\circ - 4\alpha. \quad (2.4)$$

Furthermore, recalling that $\angle DEA = \angle AEF$, we have

$$\angle AEF = 90^\circ - 2\alpha.$$

Step 2. Show that $\triangle AEF \sim \triangle PRF$.

Figure 4: descriptive captions 4

In $\triangle AEF$,

$$\begin{aligned} \angle AFE &= 180^\circ - (\angle EAF + \angle AEF) \\ &= 180^\circ - (90^\circ - \angle ACB) - (90^\circ - \angle BAC) \\ &= 180^\circ - (90^\circ - 2\gamma) - (90^\circ - 2\alpha) \\ &= 2\alpha + 2\gamma. \end{aligned}$$

Since $180^\circ = 2\alpha + 2\beta + 2\gamma$, we have

$$\angle AFE = 180^\circ - \angle ABC = 180^\circ - 2\beta.$$

Now, consider $\triangle PRF$.

$$\angle PFR = \angle EFD + \angle RFE + \angle PFD.$$

Because P and R are incenters, $\angle RFE = \angle PFE = \beta$, thus

$$\begin{aligned}\angle PFR &= 180^\circ - 2\angle ABC + \angle ABC \\ &= 180^\circ - \angle ABC = 180^\circ - 2\beta.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\angle AFE = \angle PFR. \quad (2.5)$$

Below, we let \overrightarrow{XY} denote the vector from X to Y . Let $\overrightarrow{AB} = \mathbf{b}$ and $\overrightarrow{AC} = \mathbf{c}$, and define $\overrightarrow{AD} = p\mathbf{b}$ and $\overrightarrow{AF} = q\mathbf{c}$ for real numbers p, q satisfying $0 < p, q < 1$. Note that D lies on AB and F lies on AC .

Consider the inner product of \overrightarrow{AD} and \overrightarrow{CD} . Since $\overrightarrow{AD} \cdot \overrightarrow{AC} = 0$, we have

$$\overrightarrow{AD} \cdot (\overrightarrow{AD} - \overrightarrow{AC}) = p\mathbf{b} \cdot (p\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c}) = p^2|\mathbf{b}|^2 - p(\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{c}) = 0.$$

Hence,

$$p = \frac{|\mathbf{c}| \cos \angle BAC}{|\mathbf{b}|}, \quad (0 < p < 1). \quad (2.6)$$

Similarly, from the inner product of \overrightarrow{AF} and \overrightarrow{BF} ,

$$\overrightarrow{FA} \cdot (\overrightarrow{FA} + \overrightarrow{AB}) = -q\mathbf{c} \cdot (-q\mathbf{c} + \mathbf{b}) = q^2|\mathbf{c}|^2 - q(\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{c}) = 0,$$

so that

$$q = \frac{|\mathbf{b}| \cos \angle BAC}{|\mathbf{c}|}, \quad (0 < q < 1). \quad (2.7)$$

Let $AB = c$, $BC = a$, and $CA = b$ (all real numbers). Applying the law of sines to $\triangle APF$, we have

$$\frac{AD}{\sin \frac{1}{2}\angle BAC} = \frac{PF}{\sin (90^\circ + \frac{1}{2}\angle ACB)}.$$

By substituting the geometric relations, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha \cdot b\right) \cdot \frac{\sin(90^\circ + \alpha)}{\sin \beta} = PF.$$

Thus,

$$PF = \left(\frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha \cdot b\right) \cdot \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \beta}.$$

Similarly, applying the law of sines to $\triangle CRF$ yields

$$\frac{FC}{\sin \frac{1}{2}\angle ACB} = \frac{RF}{\sin (90^\circ + \frac{1}{2}\angle BAC)}.$$

Substituting the corresponding quantities gives

$$\left(1 - \frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha\right) b \cdot \frac{\sin(90^\circ + \alpha)}{\sin \gamma} = RF.$$

Hence,

$$RF = \left(1 - \frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha\right) b \cdot \frac{\sin \gamma}{\cos \alpha}.$$

Furthermore, applying the law of sines to $\triangle CEF$, we have

$$\frac{FC}{\sin \angle ACB} = \frac{EF}{\sin \angle BAC}.$$

Substituting yields

$$\left(1 - \frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha\right) b \cdot \frac{\sin 2\alpha}{\sin \gamma} = EF.$$

That is,

$$EF = \left(1 - \frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha\right) b \cdot \frac{\sin 2\gamma}{\cos 2\alpha}.$$

Therefore,

$$AF : PF = 1 : \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \gamma}, \quad EF : RF = 1 : \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \gamma}.$$

Hence,

$$AF : PF = EF : RF. \tag{2.8}$$

Thus, $\triangle PRF \sim \triangle AEF$. Similarly, we can show that $\triangle BDF \sim \triangle PDQ$ and $\triangle CDE \sim \triangle QER$.

From these similarity relations, it follows that

$$\angle PRQ = \angle FRE - \angle FRP - \angle ERQ = 90^\circ - \gamma.$$

Likewise,

$$\angle PQR = 90^\circ - \beta, \quad \angle QPR = 90^\circ - \alpha.$$

Let the intersection of line AP with segment QR be X , that of line BQ with PR be Y , and that of line CR with PQ be Z .

Then we have

$$\angle RPX = \angle FPX - \angle FPR = \alpha + \beta - (90^\circ - 2\gamma) = \gamma,$$

and therefore

$$\angle PXR = 180^\circ - (\angle PRX + \angle RPX) = 180^\circ - (90^\circ - \gamma + \gamma) = 90^\circ.$$

Similarly,

$$\angle QYR = 90^\circ, \quad \angle RZP = 90^\circ.$$

Hence, I is the orthocenter of $\triangle PQR$.

(ii) Case of a Right $\triangle ABC$

When $\triangle ABC$ is a right triangle, some of the intersection points coincide with the vertices of the triangle. Hence, the definitions in case (i) may degenerate. Therefore, we extend the definition so that the same relation can be confirmed even in the right-angled case. Here, we consider the representative case where $\angle BCA = 90^\circ$. The other two cases, where the right angle lies at A or B , can be shown symmetrically in the same manner.

[Lemma 2] Let $\triangle ABC$ be a right triangle with $\angle BCA = 90^\circ$. Then the circle C_2 with diameter BC and the circle C_3 with diameter CA touch each other at the single point C and have no other intersection. Hence, the intersection point D of these two circles coincides with C itself.

Proof of Lemma 2. When $\angle BCA = 90^\circ$, both circles C_2 and C_3 pass through the point C , and their diameters BC and CA are perpendicular to each other. Thus, the circumferences of the two circles meet at a right angle, and they share a common tangent at C . Therefore, they intersect only at C . \square

Hence, the lemma is proved.

Because $\triangle CEF$ degenerates in this configuration, we regard the point C itself as the incenter R . Let P be the incenter of $\triangle ADC$ and Q that of $\triangle BDC$.

Proof. We will show that the incenter I and the orthocenter H coincide.

The reasoning proceeds in the same manner as in the acute case.

Figure 5: descriptive captions 5

Step 1. Show that $\triangle AED \sim \triangle PQD$.

As in the previous case, we have $\angle AEB = 90^\circ = \angle BCA$ and $\angle CFB = 90^\circ = \angle BCA$. Hence, both E and F coincide with C . Thus, $\triangle DEF$ degenerates, and the vertices D, E, F all coincide with C . \square

Therefore, $\triangle CEF$ degenerates to the single point C , and the point C itself can be regarded as both the incenter and orthocenter of the degenerate triangle. Consequently, the relation “incenter = orthocenter” is preserved, just as in the acute case.

Now, let A, B, C be the vertices of $\triangle ABC$. Draw perpendicular lines to the sides AB , BC , and CA through each vertex respectively. These three lines all pass through the point C . Therefore, the orthocenter of $\triangle ABC$ clearly coincides with C . The incenter of the degenerate $\triangle DEF$ is also C . Thus, they represent the same point.

From the property of a right triangle,

$$\angle QDP = \angle QDR + \angle PDR = 90^\circ = \angle ADE.$$

Now, by using the values of p and q derived in equations (2.6) and (2.7), and applying the law of sines to $\triangle ADP$, we have

$$\left(\frac{c}{b} \cos 2\alpha \cdot c\right) \cdot \frac{\sin(90^\circ + \gamma)}{\sin \beta} = DP.$$

Similarly,

$$\left(1 - \frac{c}{b} \cos 2\alpha\right) c \cdot \frac{\sin(90^\circ + \gamma)}{\sin \beta} = DR.$$

Furthermore,

$$\left(1 - \frac{b}{c} \cos 2\alpha\right) b \cdot \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sin 2\gamma} = EF.$$

Then we obtain

$$AD : PD = DR : DQ.$$

Hence,

$$\angle PRQ = 90^\circ - \gamma, \quad \angle PQR = 90^\circ - \beta, \quad \angle QPR = 90^\circ - \alpha.$$

Since this is equivalent to the validity of equation (2.9), the same result holds even when $\triangle ABC$ is a right triangle.

(iii) Case of an Obtuse $\triangle ABC$

When $\triangle ABC$ is obtuse, one of the intersections lies on the longest side of the triangle. Without loss of generality, we assume that

$$90^\circ < \angle ACB < 180^\circ.$$

By the inscribed angle theorem,

$$\angle BDC = 90^\circ > \angle BAC,$$

so it is easy to see that the intersection point D lies on the extension of side AB . The

other intersections occur outside the triangle (see Figure 6).

[Lemma 3] If $\triangle ABC$ is obtuse and $\angle ACB > 90^\circ$, then the intersection point D of circles C_2 and C_3 lies outside side AB , the intersection point E of C_3 and C_1 lies outside side BC , and the intersection point F of C_1 and C_2 lies outside side CA .

Proof of Lemma 3. Since $\angle ABC$ is acute, circle C_3 intersects it at two points. Because E is not a vertex C , it lies outside the triangle. By the inscribed angle theorem on circle C_1 ,

$$\angle BEA = 90^\circ.$$

Similarly, by the same theorem for circle C_3 ,

$$\angle CEA = 90^\circ.$$

Now, let Y be the foot of the perpendicular from A to BC ; then $AY \perp BC$, meaning that E and Y coincide. Hence, E lies on the line BC . The same reasoning shows that F lies on line CA . Therefore, the lemma is proved. \square

Figure 6: descriptive captions 6

Step 1. Show that H and I coincide.

From the circle theorems and the ratio formulas derived in the previous section,

$$AF : PF = EF : RF = \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \gamma}.$$

This ratio remains unchanged even when the points move to the extensions of the sides (the sign merely reverses, but the absolute value remains the same). Hence, the ratio of the corresponding sides coincides with that of the acute case, and the similarity relations among the triangles are preserved.

From Lemma 3, it follows that these relations hold along the same straight lines. By the same reasoning, the points Q and R satisfy the analogous relations.

Therefore, even in the case of an obtuse triangle, except for the fact that the points D , E , and F move onto the extensions of the sides, the same angular and side ratio relations as in the acute case are satisfied. Consequently, the similarity relations among

the triangles $\triangle PQR$ and $\triangle DEF$, etc., remain valid, and the positional relation between the incenter and the orthocenter does not change. That is, in the case of an obtuse triangle, Inner center I and orthocenter H are the same.

Therefore, from (i), (ii), and (iii), the orthocenter of $\triangle PQR$ coincides with the incenter of $\triangle ABC$.

Thus, the theorem is proved.

4 Applications of the Theorem

Proposition 1 (Theorem)

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} \cdot \frac{QE}{ER} \cdot \frac{RF}{FP} = 1$$

Proof. From Main Theorem,

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} = \frac{\sin^2 \beta}{\sin^2 \gamma}, \quad \frac{QE}{ER} = \frac{\sin^2 \gamma}{\sin^2 \alpha}, \quad \frac{RF}{FP} = \frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{\sin^2 \beta}.$$

Multiplying these equations together gives the desired result. □

Proposition 2 (Inequality).

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} + \frac{QE}{ER} + \frac{RF}{FP} \geq 3$$

Proof. Since all ratios are positive, by the AM–GM inequality and Proposition 1,

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} + \frac{QE}{ER} + \frac{RF}{FP} \geq 3 \sqrt[3]{\frac{PD}{DQ} \cdot \frac{QE}{ER} \cdot \frac{RF}{FP}} = 3.$$

□

5 Conclusion

By proving the above, we have shown that it is possible to construct a triangle whose incenter and orthocenter coincide. In this study, the relationship between the incenter and the orthocenter was investigated, but I would also like to explore whether triangles can be constructed in which other centers among the five classical centers (such as the centroid, circumcenter, or excenters) coincide.

It is likely that this phenomenon has not yet been discovered. Moreover, I expect that there exist other triangles in which several of these five centers coincide. Furthermore, it remains unclear whether the converse of the present theorem holds. I intend to continue this research including that problem. I hope that this study will contribute to the development of elementary geometry and to the broader progress of mathematics.

Summary of the Results

- The incenter of $\triangle ABC$ coincides with the orthocenter of $\triangle PQR$.
- $\angle QPR = \frac{1}{2}\angle BAC$.
- The product of the ratios satisfies

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} \cdot \frac{QE}{ER} \cdot \frac{RF}{FP} = 1.$$

- The inequality

$$\frac{PD}{DQ} + \frac{QE}{ER} + \frac{RF}{FP} \geq 3$$

also holds. (Inequality)

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